

Planning: Plan ahead

Plan & Design

Capture Key Project Information

Tracking project information helps understand applicable policies to align with the end of a research project or activity. Capture project details in DMPTool, lab/project notebooks, Harvard compliance systems, or other documentation (e.g., README File). A project may be formally defined by a funder or collaboration, however, sometimes projects are informally defined between a researcher and the PI.

- **Project ID:** Determined by the funder and/or institution (e.g., NIH grant number)
- **Project Name:** As it appears on the grant or the understood name of an informal collaboration
- **Project PI:** Name and ORCID of Principal Investigator(s) or main researcher(s) on the project
- **Project Description/Abstract:** Provide background and rationale about the project
- **Administrative Data:** Contact details, project dates, data management plan versions, etc.

★ **Create and connect your [ORCID account](#) with Harvard University**

Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID) is an alphanumeric code to uniquely identify scientific and other academic authors and contributors. Connecting your ORCID to Harvard authorizes the university to read your public data and authenticates the Harvard-based activities listed in your ORCID record.

Review Relevant Policies for Data Management

Universities, funders, and publishers all have expectations and requirements for research data related to security, sharing and retention.

- **[Harvard Research Data Security Policy \(HRDSP\)](#):** Focuses on proper management and stewardship of research data, inclusive of human subjects' research, data exchanged pursuant to a data use agreement (DUA), and other data subject to foreign, federal, or state regulations, sponsor requirements or intellectual property protections.
- **[Harvard DUA Guidance and Policy](#):** A Data Use Agreement (DUA) is a binding contract between organizations that governs the transfer and use of data. It is an agreement between the data producer and secondary data user(s) and may impose rules for reuse, storage, re-dissemination, and disposal or termination. DUA terms and conditions vary depending on the specific type of data. DUAs are considered research-related agreements and must be reviewed and signed by an appropriate Negotiating Office at Harvard.

- [Harvard Research Records Retention](#): Researchers have certain obligations to record, maintain and retain research records, and to make those records available for grant monitoring and auditing purposes. In general, essential research records should be retained for a period of no fewer than seven (7) years after the end of a research project or activity.
- [Data Management and Sharing Policies](#): Requirements for researchers to make their data available to others when they complete a study. Most commonly to be compliant with funding organizations (e.g., NIH/NSF) and journals (e.g., Nature/Science) that require the reporting of research data.

Write or Review a Data Management and Sharing Plan

A [data management and sharing plan](#) (DMSP or DMS Plan) is a formal document that outlines what you will do with your data during and after a research project. A DMS Plan is now commonly required as a condition of funding for top funders, such as [NIH](#) and [NSF](#). You may be tasked with writing this DMS Plan, or if one has already been developed for your project, you should review the Plan in collaboration with the PI.

★ *Collaboratively write and track your DMS Plan in [DMPTool](#)*

DMPTool is an online tool available to help you write your data management and sharing plans according to funder requirements and Harvard policies for managing your data. Login with HarvardKey and request help through Harvard Library's Data Management Plan Review Service.

Budget for Data Management and Sharing

PIs might want to be aware of associated costs for data management resources, including understanding where costs will be accrued, who pays those costs, and who has managerial responsibility for them will inform management activities throughout the project. For example, NIH allows investigators to request funds toward data management and sharing in the budget sections of their applications. Harvard University has [guidance for budgeting data management and sharing costs](#) for PIs.

Define Roles and Responsibilities

It is recommended that PIs select a dedicated individual responsible for research data to ensure the ongoing data management practices on each project. Data management responsibilities extend beyond just the PI or researcher who created or collected the data. Various parties are involved in the research process and may play a role in ensuring good quality data stewardship. The [roles and responsibilities of data management](#) should be clearly defined.

- **Department, Lab, or Project Data Manager:** Responsible for ensuring the accurate collection, documentation, storage, and reporting of data throughout the department, lab, or project. Explore [resources to get started](#) with and support ongoing data management practices.

□ Establish Data Organization

Describe locations where your data are stored and your file naming and folder structure conventions. Research data files and folders need to be labeled and organized in a systematic way agreed upon by the entire research team, so they're both identifiable and accessible for current and future users. It is important that access to research data is shared with the PI and, as appropriate, other project collaborators. Research data should always be stored in School-approved storage locations and not on personal laptop or desktop devices.

- **File Naming:** A file naming convention is a framework for naming your files in a way that describes what they contain and how they relate to other files. Everyone on the team needs to be consistent.
- **File Structure:** Create folders according to file naming conventions, document their purpose, and ensure files are stored in correct folders.

□ Keep Up to Date with Data Management Resources and Policies

Many relevant training courses are offered at Harvard University; another resource is lab data managers. There may be required training for specific roles, for example working with sensitive data.

- **Research Data Management Seminars:** Regular classes and workshops on a variety of topics related to the management of research data.
- **Harvard Research Data Security Training:** We recommend that researchers handling secure data complete the Harvard University developed training on the information security policy.
- **CITI Human Research Training:** Harvard institutional policies require all individuals who are involved in human subjects' research to complete training in the ethical conduct of human research.

★ **Utilize the [RDM Onboarding Checklist](#) to onboard new employees or trainees to a lab or new project**

The RDM Onboarding Checklist outlines the important steps for new employees or trainees to understand the data management practices of the lab or project, ensuring accurate communication throughout the lifecycle.